

TENSION, COMPRESSION AND FLEXURE PROPERTIES OF PULTRUDED COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: Pultruded glass fiber reinforced polymer matrix composites have been tested in tension, three-point bending, four-point bending and compression. In each case, twenty identical specimens have been tested and a Weibull analysis has been conducted. The measured and Weibull-predicted ratios of bending strength to tensile strength are compared. The shape parameter and the characteristic strength for each type of loading are presented. The thickness of the composite and the angle between the pultrusion direction and the loading are two of the interesting parameters. The elastic modulus measured under different types of load is compared. Extensive measurements, such as load-deflection in bending and back-to-back strains, end-shortening, strains across the thickness in compression, have been made.

KEYWORDS: Tension, compression, flexure, Weibull analysis, pultruded composites.

INTRODUCTION

A number of composites with a polymeric matrix and continuous fiber reinforcements are brittle because of the brittleness of the constituents. Therefore, such composites exhibit the well-known size-effects or stress-gradient effects. In other words, fracture failure of such materials depends not only on the highest stress magnitude, but also on the volume of material on which this highest stress acts. There are two important manifestations of the stress-gradient effect: the tensile strength is less than the four-point flexural strength which is less than the three-point flexural strength; the second manifestation is the hole-size effect, which has led to the development of the 'characteristic dimension' (similar to the Neuber's elementary block for metals).

There are two important consequences of the stress-gradient effect. The first raises the question, which distribution function should be used for processing the test results for such materials - normal or Weibull? The second consequence is the feasibility of conducting flexure tests, which are easy to conduct, and predict the tensile strength, which is very difficult to directly measure for very brittle materials.

The Weibull distribution function or the Weibull analysis has been applied to many materials, with varying degrees of success. Weil and Daniel [1] applied the Weibull analysis to brittle steel, graphite and ceramics. Knight and Hahn [2] applied the Weibull analysis to randomly oriented short-fiber reinforced composites. The application of a two-parameter Weibull model to the analysis of four-point flexure and tensile coupon data for unidirectional graphite-epoxy composites is reported in Ref. 3. Excellent agreement between measured values and Weibull predictions for the ratio of three-point flexure strength to tensile strength has been reported. However, the conclusion of Ref. 4 is the opposite; in this work, unidirectional graphite-epoxy data, as well as both three-point and four-point bending test data, were obtained, while including the influence of specimen thickness. The authors concluded that the experimental results did not correlate with a two-parameter Weibull statistical model, for tensile tests conducted parallel to the reinforcement direction.

Prabhakaran and Saha [5] conducted tension and flexure tests on pultruded composites, with various geometrical parameters, and concluded that the two-parameter Weibull analysis is applicable to such materials.

In the present investigation, the Weibull two-parameter model has been applied to yet another class of composites, namely pultruded, glass fiber reinforced polymeric, composites. In addition to the tensile, three-point flexure and four-point flexure tests, compression tests also have been performed. In some of the cases, specimens parallel and perpendicular to the pultrusion direction have been tested; also, specimens with different thicknesses have been investigated.

THE TEST MATERIAL: PULTRUDED COMPOSITE

In civil engineering infrastructural applications, pultruded composites are finding increasing use because of the ease of fabrication, corrosion resistance and light weight. Unlike aerospace composites, the pultruded composites have not been investigated thoroughly. Even standard tests, such as tension, compression and flexure, have not been conducted extensively. The lay-up of pultruded composites, the manufacturing processes, etc., are sufficiently different from the well-understood aerospace composites to warrant a thorough investigation of the basic properties. It has been found [6] that the character of the various layers (plies) as well as the glass content in these layers are different for pultruded sheets of different thicknesses. For this reason, specimens from pultruded sheets of more than one thickness were tested in this investigation.

TENSION AND FLEXURE LOADING

To facilitate discussion, the tensile, three-point flexure and four-point flexure data will be considered together. These three types of tests were performed on specimens fabricated from 3.2 mm and 12.7 mm thick pultruded sheets, parallel (referred to as 0°) and perpendicular (referred to as 90°) to the pultrusion direction. Each type of test was performed on a set of twenty identical specimens. The specimens were 12.7 mm wide. The 3.2 mm thick tensile specimens were 18 cm

long and the flexure specimens were 6 cm to 8 cm long; one of the objectives was to keep the volume of material in the test section the same in all the tests. The 12.7 mm thick tensile specimens were 25 cm long and the flexure specimens were 15 cm long. The specimens were all strain gaged back-to-back and the deflection of the flexure specimens was measured by a dial gage. The tests were all repeatable. The tensile stress-strain behavior obtained for the 12.7 mm thick, 0° specimen is shown in Fig. 1. This figure shows that the tensile stress-strain response exhibited in the three tests is practically identical. It was observed that there was good agreement between the stress-strain responses for the tension and compression sides of flexure specimens also. The load-central deflection responses of the three-point and four-point specimens were also repeatable and fairly linear.

Fig. 1: Tensile stress-strain response from tensile, three-point flexure, and four-point flexure tests.

The two-parameter Weibull distribution function was used to analyze the experimental results. The probability of survival for the 12.7 mm thick, 90° specimens under the three types of loading is shown in Fig. 2 as a function of the stress. As expected, the curve for the three-point flexure loading is at the right and the curve for the axial tension loading is at the left, with the curve for the four-point flexure loading in the middle, but near the line for the three-point flexure.

It is possible to show from basic considerations that for simple tension under uniform stress conditions,

$$S_t = S_o (V_t)^{-\frac{1}{m}} \quad (1)$$

where S_t is the strength under tensile loading, S_o is the Weibull characteristic strength, m is the Weibull shape parameter and V_t is the volume of material subjected to the highest tensile stress.

Fig. 2: Survivability plot for 12.7 mm thick, 90° specimens under tensile, three-point flexure and four-point flexure loading

Considering the stress distributions in the three-point and four-point flexure specimens, it is possible to develop the following equations for the strength ratios:

$$\frac{S_b}{S_t} = \left[2(m+1)^2 \left(\frac{V_t}{V_b} \right) \right]^{\frac{1}{m}} \quad (3\text{-point}) \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{S_b}{S_t} = \left[\frac{4(m+1)^2}{(m+2)} \left(\frac{V_t}{V_b} \right) \right]^{\frac{1}{m}} \quad (4\text{-point}) \quad (3)$$

where S_b is the bending strength.

The Weibull shape parameter, m , experimentally determined for tension, three-point bending and four-point bending for the specimens with 3.2 mm and 12.7 mm thicknesses, with orientations 0°

and 90°, is presented in Table 1. It is seen that except for the 90°, 12.7 mm thickness case, the m values fall in a narrow range of 14.0 to 18.8. As the m value tends to be larger for smaller scatter in the test results, it is remarkable that the 90°, 12.7 mm thick specimens show a much smaller scatter, especially under direct tensile loading; this is probably due to the combination of the roving fibers placed perpendicular to the tensile load and the thicker sheet having appreciable porosity. Interestingly, Bullock [3] reported the same m value for the three types of loading while Whitney [4] reported different values.

Table 1: Weibull shape parameter, m , for tension, three-point flexure and four-point flexure

Angle	Thickness	Tension	3-Point Flexure	4-Point Flexure
0°	3.2 mm	15.5	15.4	15.3
0°	12.7 mm	18.0	17.1	16.6
90°	3.2 mm	18.8	15.3	14.0
90°	12.7 mm	50.8	20.8	26.6

The strength ratios calculated from Eqns 2 and 3 and experimentally determined are presented in Table 2. The strength ratios are very close in some cases but quite different in others. There appears to be no clear trend. A few attempts were made to calculate the strength ratios based on the bending specimen volume on the tension side only, bending specimen localized volume (a thin layer) on the tension side, etc., but no improvements in the trends could be seen.

Table 2: Measured and Weibull-predicted strength ratios

Angle	Thickness	3-Point Flexure		4-Point Flexure	
		Measured	Weibull	Measured	Weibull
0°	3.2 mm	1.29	1.53	1.13	1.34
0°	12.7 mm	1.45	1.46	1.30	1.34
90°	3.2 mm	1.64	1.46	1.52	1.31
90°	12.7 mm	1.61	1.39	1.54	1.24

COMPRESSION LOADING

In general, compression tests are more difficult to perform compared to tensile and flexure tests. This is because the requirements for uniform compression loading and for prevention of buckling are quite stringent. For this investigation special arrangements, such as swivelling compression loading fixture, anti-buckling attachments and parallelism of the loaded edges were made. Twenty identical short block compression specimens were tested, with 0° orientation and with 6.3 mm and 12.7 mm thicknesses. The uniformity of loading was verified by mounting five electrical resistance strain gages across the 25.4 mm wide specimen and monitoring these strains all the way to compression failure. The compression specimens were 44.5 mm high.

The probability of survival for the two sets of compression specimens is presented as a function of the stress in Fig. 3. The curve for the thinner material is to the right, consistent with the observation that the thicker material has significant porosity.

Fig. 3: Survivability plots for 6.3 mm and 12.7 mm thick, 0° specimens under compressive loading.

The experimentally determined Young’s modulus, Poisson’s ratio, Weibull characteristic strength and the shape parameter are presented in Table 3. While the modulus and Poisson’s ratio are comparable for the two thicknesses, the thinner material is noticeably stronger in compression. The shape parameter, m , however, is remarkably close for the two thicknesses. A comparison of this Table with Table 1 shows that the shape parameter for compression is slightly larger than that for tension or flexure.

Table 3: Compression properties of 6.3 mm and 12.7 mm thick specimens

Property	Compression	
	6.3 mm thick	12.7 mm thick
Young’s Modulus, E (GPa)	17.86	17.91
ν	0.314	0.309
Weibull characteristic strength, (MPa)	273.32	251.42
Shape parameter	21.0	22.2

CONCLUSIONS

Results from extensive tests on pultruded composites have been presented. These tests were conducted on specimens with two different orientations and with different thicknesses. Four different types of loads were applied: tension, compression, three-point flexure and four-point flexure. In each case, twenty identical specimens were tested. A two-parameter Weibull analysis was conducted on each set of results. The shape parameter, while not exactly a constant, did fall in a fairly narrow range in all cases. The measured ratio of flexure strength to tensile strength did not agree with the ratio calculated on the basis of the Weibull analysis. It is concluded that while the pultruded composites investigated were brittle enough to justify the application of the Weibull analysis, the flaw distribution (as seen from a microstructural examination) was not uniform enough to result in a predictable strength ratio.

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